

From BIM to FEM: An ANSYS Case Study

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Abstract

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is relied upon to manage both the visual and functional aspects of buildings. However, transferring this data into Finite Element Analysis (FEA) platforms like ANSYS for structural analysis presents significant challenges such as geometry discontinuities, Boolean operation failures, and difficulties in translating material properties. To address these challenges, the research proposes a methodology to improve the accuracy and efficiency of data transfer from BIM to ANSYS.

A case study of a simplified bridge model, consisting of a girder beam, pier, piles, and a pier cap is used to test the methodology. Two workflows, Dynamo to ANSYS and IFC to ANSYS, are evaluated for their ability to transfer data while maintaining model integrity. The model is transferred as a wireframe using the SAT format in the Dynamo-to-ANSYS workflow. In contrast, in the IFC-to-ANSYS workflow, the model is transferred as solid geometry via formats such as STEP and IGES, with IFC acting as an intermediate. The Structural Analysis Format (SAF) is also tested by transferring the same bridge model from ArchiCAD to SCIA Engineer and FEM-Design for comparison. Static structural and modal analyses are performed on the model in different formats to assess their ability to handle

model complexities and ensure consistency in data transfer. Metrics such as mesh quality, deformations, bending moments, modal shapes, and effective mass ratios are used to assess the effectiveness of each workflow.

Through these investigations, the study identifies the strengths of different workflows for transferring data from BIM to ANSYS. While challenges such as the unidirectional nature of the methodology and the handling of more complex geometries remain, formats like SAF offer promising opportunities for further automation of the data transfer process.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/zi2F1bSF8kQ>

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